

A federated FAIR platform enabling large-scale analysis of high-value cohort data connecting Europe and Canada in personalized health

Horizon 2020 - SC1-2018

Topic SC1-BHC-05-2018

Research and Innovation Programme

Grant Agreement H2020 – 824989

WP7: ELSI, governance, dissemination and sustainability

Deliverable D7.1: Governance context appraisal

Account of the existing regulatory context, challenges and issues (including for the governance of the DataSHIELD infrastructure and multi-center studies in general), and stakeholder expectations of data sharing and data governance

- *Document Information*

Description	Governance Context Appraisal
Dissemination level	PU
Contractual date of delivery	31/03/2023
Actual date of delivery	29/06/2023
Work package No	WP7
Deliverable number	D7.1
Status	Final document
Version	V1.0
WP contributing to the deliverable	WP7
Task responsible	ULIV
Other contributors	
Author(s)	Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI-ERIC), Kaya Akyüz (BBMRI-ERIC), Melanie Goisaufl (BBMRI-ERIC), Becca Wilson (ULIV), Demetris Avraam (ULIV)
Reviewed by	Morris Swertz (UMCG), Sylvain Sebert (Oulu), Tom Bishop (UCAM), Eleanor Hyde (UMCG)
Approved by	Morris Swertz (UMCG)
EC Project Officer	Jana Makedonska

Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

- *Document Abbreviations*

BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
DPO	Data Protection Officer
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EC	European Commission
ECOUTER	Employing Conceptual schema for policy and translation engagement in research
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EEA	European Economic Area
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
RI	Research Infrastructure

• *Table of Contents*

• Document Information	1
• Document Abbreviations	2
• Table of Contents	3
1. Executive summary	4
2. Introduction	5
2.1. Purpose	5
2.2. Intended Audience	5
2.3. Methods	5
2.4. Ongoing Work	5
3. Governance Context Appraisal: DataSHIELD	5
4. Discussion	8
5. References	8

1. Executive summary

Access to research data is constrained by ethico-legal and social considerations and by data governance restrictions. Data may be of a sensitive nature and/or may not be held by the researcher's own organisation. The principal aim of EUCAN-connect is to accelerate multi-center studies that enable data pooling to increase statistical power, in particular using federated data analysis approaches such as DataSHIELD. The principal aim of DataSHIELD is to enable remote statistical analysis/co-analysis of data in real time, while actively mitigating disclosure risk through a multi-layered system of disclosure-preventing mechanisms. DataSHIELD is not implemented in isolation, but has been designed to operate in tandem with disclosure protections and mitigations represented as formal regulatory and professional conditions for data use and best practice. This report concludes that DataSHIELD has set up good governance components by mitigating data disclosure risks.

2. Introduction

2.1. Purpose

The major objective of this report is to conclude the governance context appraisal building on D7.2 (governance model) and D7.3 (sustainability). It understands DataSHIELD as a key element for federated data sharing.

2.2. Intended Audience

This document is to be used as a reference for:

- all consortium partners of EUCAN-Connect;
- maintainers of participating catalogues;
- current and future consortia embarking on transnational federated data sharing;
- multi-centre cohort studies.

2.3. Methods

This deliverable builds on publications resulting from the project (published or in preparation) and draws on exchanges with WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7 throughout the duration of the project. Social science data collection and analysis was undertaken for the purposes of context appraisal and evaluation of the development of data harmonisation and federated analysis (DataSHIELD) infrastructures to further inform the development of responsible governance of federated data analysis.

2.4. Ongoing Work

The legal review of the DataSHIELD data lifecycle is yet to be completed (expected Q4/2023).

3. Governance Context Appraisal: DataSHIELD

The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is the strongest data privacy and security law in the world. While it has global reach, it also allows national derogations as regards data use for research (Slokenberga et al, eds 2021). The rapid evolution of legal requirements applicable to data use, however, has the potential to outstrip the capabilities of networks of biomedical data users to respond to the shifting norms. Furthermore, it could, potentially, also delegitimize established institutional bodies that are responsible for assessing and authorising the downstream use of data, including research ethics committees and institutional data custodians. In a globalising technoscientific landscape where increased datafication and internationalisation of research is a key characteristic, these burdens are especially pronounced for clinical and research networks that are of transnational scale, because the legal compliance burden for outbound international data transfers from the European

Economic Area (EEA) is especially high. Besides contractual obligations and the use of data through secure processing environments, the use of federated data analysis methodologies should be pursued by data controllers/processors and potentially law makers as Bernier et al (2023) suggest. Naturally, any governance framework needs to be solid and enable addressing potential tensions and conflicts including the following (adapted from Murtagh et al, 2021):

- What issues or practices might be a source or cause of tension?
- Who is responsible for managing or responding to tension?
- How could responses to people's concerns or differences of opinion avoid blame, shame, or stigma, and instead, create better outcomes for all?
- How can the initiative support better engagement between (internal and external) stakeholders so that it fosters an open and trusting environment?
- How are activities, intentions and findings/outcomes being communicated in ways that encourage diverse feedback?
- How can different perspectives work together constructively?
- How are tensions and conflicts resolved and managed at different levels and times in the project?
- How will differing or conflicting perspectives be accommodated and accounted for?
- How is it ensured that all stakeholders are heard and understood?
- How do they acknowledge disagreements (including amongst themselves) and are responsive to different perspectives?

Efforts of transforming 'cohorts' as 'collections of data collected and organised for a specific function' into part of a data ecosystem involves balancing valuing practices against rigid structures and their socio-technical conditions, especially requiring various forms of work and infrastructuring around reuse, harmonisation, standardisation, etc. (Mayrhofer et al, 2023, submitted). Furthermore, certain forms of data, such as human genomic data bear risks of identifiability by their nature when publically available, thus necessitating new understandings and practices regarding privacy, anonymity and data security (Akyüz et al, 2023).

In parallel to documenting cohort studies and exploring harmonisation potential, it is essential to determine the operating model and build the infrastructure required to host, manage, and analyse the data (Fortier et al 2023). In practice, it is furthermore critical to establish clear roles and responsibilities to ensure not only financial but also organisational sustainability, e.g., by including training (Akyüz et al, 2023). At the same time, identifying, mitigating and communicating risks should be undertaken in a manner that sees risk governance as a continuous and adaptive aspect of life sciences research and infrastructures (Akyüz et al, 2021).

Access to research data is often constrained by ethico-legal and social considerations and by data governance restrictions. Data, in many cases, could be sensitive and not held by the researcher's own organisation. It is widely acknowledged that gaining access to such data can be time-consuming due to having to fulfil the data governance requirements associated with such data, and technical challenges may rise in having to physically move and store large data volumes. Further to this, modern research necessitates the analysis of data collaboratively or from more than one source, where data sources are not usually co-located in a central data warehouse. Federated analysis tools attempt to alleviate these problems by permitting researchers to perform analysis on sensitive data at their source, without necessitating the physical transfer of data in the sensitive form into either a central data warehouse or directly to the researcher. DataSHIELD is one such tool that allows remote statistical analysis of data in real time while mitigating disclosure risk by an active multi-layer system of mechanisms that are designed to reduce the possibility of disclosure. DataSHIELD facilitates research based on data held at one or multiple sites , in settings where:

1. Analysis/co-analysis of microdata (i.e. per person data) is scientifically necessary but ethico-legal or other governance considerations relating to the (potential) sensitivity of the data from a personal perspective either hinder or prevent the release/sharing of at least some of the required data. As a result, data access/analysis is rendered unacceptably slow or impossible.
2. A research group wishes to share the information held in its data with others – e.g. to contribute to a large consortium-based analysis - but does not wish to cede control of the governance of those data (including the intellectual property or commercial assets they may represent) by physically handing over the data themselves.
3. A dataset that is to be shared/analysed contains data objects (e.g. images or 'omics structures such as whole genome DNA sequences) which are so large that it is impractical to physically transfer them to the site of analysis.

The principal aim of DataSHIELD is to enable remote statistical analysis/co-analysis of data in real time, while actively mitigating disclosure risk. Although there is some overlap between the various methods that DataSHIELD controls disclosure risk, our current standard description identifies a set of key components that jointly comprise the disclosure protection systems, which fall in three broad classes as described by Avraam et al (2023, manuscript¹):

(i) system protection elements including: data encryption, network security, secure infrastructure

¹ CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services) until published.

- (ii) analysis protection elements including: direct disclosure checks on outputs, the running of only authorised analysis functions, analytic command logs,
- (iii) governance protection elements including: data access/transfer agreements and data access request processes, user registration and password management, sanctions policy, management of the DataSHIELD disclosure control settings by the data custodian

4. Discussion

There always exists a risk of disclosure when analysing sensitive health research data, often accidental rather than through malicious intent. By mitigating disclosure risk through an active multi-layer technical and social system of disclosure-preventing mechanisms, DataSHIELD has set up a critical element of good governance. DataSHIELD is a solid tool and adaptable for the fast-moving context of health research and its current regulatory landscape in the (re)making. As recently as 23 June 2023, for instance, the Data Governance Act (DGA) entered into force and will be applicable across Europe as early as from September 2023. The DGA is a legal instrument intended to support the set-up and development of common European data spaces in strategic domains such as health for increasing data availability, reuse and trust in data sharing. Another example include the different levels of infrastructures existing in Europe ranging from data resources and research infrastructures of European scale to national infrastructures and their strategic roadmaps² that are ultimately building blocks for the realisation of the ambitious European Health Data Space (EHDS), 'a health specific ecosystem comprised of rules, common standards and practices, infrastructures and a governance framework'³ that aims at empowering individuals, fostering the single market and providing a trustworthy set-up by design for secondary use of data. For all this, DataSHIELD has all the governance components in place to be one tool for its realisation.

5. References

Akyüz K, Chassang G, Goisauf M, Kozera Ł, Meżinska S, Tzortzatou O, Mayrhofer MT. Biobanking and risk assessment: a comprehensive typology of risks for an adaptive risk governance. *Life Sci Soc Policy*. 2021 Dec 13;17(1):10. doi: [10.1186/s40504-021-00117-7](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40504-021-00117-7)

Akyüz K, Goisauf M, Chassang G, Kozera L, Meżinska S, Tzortzatou-Nanopoulou O, & Mayrhofer MT (2023). Post-identifiability in changing sociotechnological genomic data environments. *BioSocieties*. doi: [10.1057/s41292-023-00299-7](https://doi.org/10.1057/s41292-023-00299-7)

²https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/esfri_en.

³ <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/>

Akyüz K, Goisau M, & Mayrhofer MT (2023). EUCAN-Connect Deliverable D7.3: Sustainability Plan. Zenodo. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7520191](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520191)

Avraam, D, Wilson RC, Wheeler B, Marcon Y, Butters O, Garner H, Gonçalves G, Haakma S, Swertz M, Hyde E, Banerjee S, Bishop T, Escribà Montagut X, Gonzalez JR, Morgan A, Pinot de Moira A, Cadman T, Strandberg-Larsen K, Cederkvist Kristiansen L, Nybo Andersen A, Hartlev M, Murtagh M & Burton P (2023). DataSHIELD: Mitigating disclosure risk in a multi-site federated analysis platform (manuscript in preparation, , **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services until published))

Bernier A, Molnár-Gábor F, Knoppers BM, Borry P, Cesar PMDG, Devriendt T, Goisau M, Murtagh M, Jiménez PN, Recuero M, Rial-Sebbag E, Shabani M, Wilson RC, Zaccagnini D, Maxwell L. Reconciling the biomedical data commons and the GDPR: three lessons from the EUCAN ELSI collaboratory. *Eur J Hum Genet.* 2023 Jun 15. doi: [10.1038/s41431-023-01403-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-023-01403-y)

Fortier I, Wey TW, Bergeron J, Pinot de Moira A, Nybo-Andersen AM, Bishop T, Murtagh MJ, Miočević M, Swertz MA, van Enckevort E, Marcon Y, Mayrhofer MT, Ornelas JP, Sebert S, Santos AC, Rocha A, Wilson RC, Griffith LE, Burton P. Life course of retrospective harmonization initiatives: key elements to consider. *J Dev Orig Health Dis.* 2023 Apr;14(2):190-198. doi: [10.1017/S2040174422000460](https://doi.org/10.1017/S2040174422000460)

Mayrhofer MT., Akyüz K & Goisau M. Re/valuing data/infrastructures: How are cohorts as collections transformed into a moral economy of data use? (manuscript in preparation).

Murtagh MJ, Machirori M, Gaff CL, Blell MT, de Vries J, Doerr M, Dove ES, Duncanson A, Hastings Ward J, Hendricks-Sturup R, Ho CWL, Johns A, Joly Y, Kato K, Katsui K, Kumuthini J, Maleady-Crowe F, Middleton A, Milne R, Minion JT, Matshaba M, Mulrine S, Patch C, Ryan R, Viney W. Engaged genomic science produces better and fairer outcomes: an engagement framework for engaging and involving participants, patients and publics in genomics research and healthcare implementation. *Wellcome Open Res.* 2021 Nov 15;6:311. doi: [10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17233.1](https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.17233.1)

Slokenberga S, Tzortzatou O, Reichel J (2021). Introduction. In: Slokenberga S, Tzortzatou O, Reichel J (eds) *GDPR and Biobanking. Law, Governance and Technology Series*, vol 43. Springer, Cham. doi: [10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_1)